

**CSR PLAYS VITOL ROLE FOR STUDENTS CAREER IN INDUSTRY AND ACADEMIA
SPECIALLY DURING COVID 19**

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Abstract

CSR means Corporate Social Responsibility which gives hands to needy people .They are playing very important role for various aspect of socity.In Bhiwandi block some NGO helps the school with the help of CSR. They are focusing on their quality education and industrial development.

The covid-19 - the infectious disease triggered by corona virus has been considered as global pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO). This contagious disease tremendously disrupted the socio-economic circumstances of the whole world. Social distancing plays a pivotal role in order to mitigate the spread of this deadly infection. Observing the present crisis situation, corporate have emerged out as a knight in shining armor and have played a significant role in creating of social distancing as an aid to mitigate the spread of this deadly infection – covid-19 and has provided basic resources to underprivileged section to combat the tough situation .

CSR is a “self-regulating business model” that implies the procedures of interaction by a company with its stakeholders and the general public at large, creating a scenario of being socially responsible. Like it is rightly said, ‘Money belongs to you, but resources belong to the society’. In view of the spread of COVID-19 and the decision of the Government of India to treat this as a notified disaster, was quick to clarify that spending of CSR funds for COVID-19 shall be considered as an eligible CSR activity. Between the needed one and the provider the NGO’s are playing vital role. They have really emerged out as a real supporter. The present study describe the initiatives taken by various NGO’s in support with the corporate thus to provide a relief and aid to restructure the lives those who suffered the most during the pandemic situation. The data was collected through primary and secondary sources and the research is primarily descriptive in nature .The data has been collected mainly from the NGO’s operational in Bhiwandi Block, Thane District, of Maharashtra. The study has shown that during pandemic companies have supported the society in varied ways. With the help of local NGO’s the corporate have tried to provide the help to the deprived section and thus act as a warrior to fight against the odds of life aroused out of the present pandemic situation.

Keywords: - CSR activity, Covid – 19, Business models, NGO’s

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Introduction:

With growing awareness about corporate social responsibility (CSR) among stakeholders, achieving social goals is as

important as delivering shareholder value and profitability. “Corporate Social Responsibility” or CSR is a concept that aims to make a company socially accountable to itself, its stakeholders, and the public at large. Through their CSR practices, companies are conscious of the kind of impact they have on all aspects of society including economic, social, and environmental. It is a way of giving back to the society for the various resources it uses to run its business.

Earlier the NGO's were taking grants from the government and the corporate and doing the social work or providing the help to the needed one. Corporate and NGO's working together concept is not a new one. It's been long ago that CSR activities are done only this way. As the time passes the government found that the duties are not fulfilled in a right way. The end users are not getting all benefits that are meant to them. This need of an hour bring the new sustainable model. The model on which they working is where the NGO's are not from outside they are the part of the company. Companies launch their own NGO's to do the CSR activity and fulfill their duties.

In last few years, CSR in India has acquired new impetus with the companies Act 2013. The Act defines that company with a net worth of rupees 500 crores or more, or a turnover of rupees 1,000 crores or more, or earning a net profit of rupees 5 crores or more must spend a minimum amount on corporate social responsibility. The announcement to allow funds spent on COVID-19 relief work as CSR spend has created a win-win situation for companies

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Today, the entire world is facing and overcoming a crisis of a magnitude which no one had anticipated. The much-dreaded Corona virus (COVID-19), a pandemic declared by the World Health Organization, has shaken the entire world and the economy at large.

Since the COVID-19 pandemic reached India, the focus of NGOs and CSR funders has been—correctly—on addressing immediate relief activities, from providing supplies to migrants to giving targeted support to end-beneficiaries. However, this near-term work may have an unintended adverse long-term impact on NGOs, especially those with significant CSR funding. The announcement to allow funds spent on COVID-19 relief work as CSR spend has created a win-win situation for the corporate.

This step was welcomed by Corporate India. The announcement to allow funds spent on COVID-19 relief work as CSR spend created a win-win situation for companies having an existing CSR obligation, who wanted to contribute to relief work and meet statutory requirements of the Companies Act at the same time. The response to the Government's call to support COVID-19 efforts has been overwhelming. Crores have been donated to various Government funds.

It was also found that many corporate who were looking for NGO partners working in the areas where they have factories, plants or other setups. Those in remote or rural areas are especially well-versed with the existing challenges of those communities and the compounding effect that COVID-19 would have. Moreover, they feel connected to the struggles of those in the area after having worked there.

There are few Case studies of Bhiwandi Block, Thane district of Maharashtra, shown the efforts of NGO and companies doing CSR activity successfully during this pandemic.

Objectives and Methodology: -

- 1) To study the initiative taken by NGO with support of companies during covid 19.
- 2) To discover the various models developed to restructure lives of affected community.

The nature of data used for this is blend of primary and secondary and the type of research is descriptive and case base research method is applied to comprehend the research.

Restructuring Lives through Corporate – NGO Collaborative Model:
1) – Cannon India pvt ltd And HUMANA (People to people India)

- HUMANA people to people to India is a development organization registered as a non-profit organization under section 25 of the company act 1956 as of 21st may 1998. The main aim of the project is to providing the knowledge and skill to those individuals and community who need assistance to come out of the poverty and filthy condition.
- Humana people to people India is working in Bhiwandi block since five years. They adopted a whole village called **KARANJOTI** in **Wadvali cluster** of Bhiwand block for developing the village, schools and people living there.
- Cannon India pvt ltd takes pride to be socially inclined towards the efficient and sustainable CSR projects. The company works on the 4E CSR policy that is Education, Eye Care, Environment and Empowerment. These are the basic ground are on which they are working. Cannon India Works with Humana since last two decades.
- During the covid 19 and lockdown in all over India HUMANA plays an important role for the people of **KARANJOTI village**. With the help of Cannon India, Humana people to people India providing a lot of help like, awareness and knowledge about covid 19, medicines, 300 food packages, 102 masks, and 50 PPE kit also for the people as well as the doctors of the village. They not only work for this village but also, providing the help at so many other places. This really shown as motivational and appreciable work done by company and NGO.

2) – Voltas India Company and LSF (Learning space Foundation)

- LSF (learning space foundation) has been actively supporting local rural communities in areas of **Wada, Bhiwandi, and Palghar** with education, livelihood, capacity building & community development programmes, for over last one decade.
- As the lockdown went into its 2.0 Phase, LSF decided to support families that comprise of daily wage workers in farms and brick-kilns across our immediate areas of purview in **Wada & Bhiwandi**, that were on the brink of starvation, and **LSF** team has been supporting them with essential dry ration and other essentials to fight the **Covid-19** outbreak, from 10th April 2020 onwards.
- The urgent need for **cloth masks, hand sanitizers, soap bars**, etc. in the rural community has also drawn need to appeal to our funding partners to step in to the **Covid-19** relief support.
- With the help of Voltas India LSF provide 1800 food packets, Hand sanitizers, Awareness about covid 19, and most important they provide the help for migrate the labour class to other states from where they belong.
- Voltas India and LSF has done a tremendous job to provide the help of these villages and still continue doing it by each passing day as the covid is still on a roaring position.

3) – Amazon care and Indian Women and Children Foundation

- Indian women and children foundation was started in 2002 with the aim of providing primary education to under privileged children and women of India. IWCF has adopted a cluster of Zilla parishad schools which includes 10 to 15 Zilla parishad schools of Bhiwandi block.
- IWCF providing the quality education to the children and also arranging the training program for the teachers of those schools with the help of sponsor companies.

- During the period of covid 19 lockdown IWCF provide various kind of help to those schools with the Amazon care. Like mask distribution, 200 food distribution, 230 sanitary kit distribution and spreading awareness.

Conclusion: -

Earlier the NGO's were taking grants from the government and other authorized agencies in order to provide the support to the underprivileged section. As the time passes the government found that the duties are not fulfilled in a right way. The end users are not getting all benefits that are meant to them. This need of an hour bring the new sustainable model. The model on which they working is where the NGO's are not from outside they are the part of the company. Companies launch their own NGO's to do the CSR activity and fulfill their duties. However on the other side Corporate collaborates with NGO's in order to carry out their CSR activities thus to support the underprivileged community at also to take steps towards sustainability.

But this is not for every business organizations. Some of them are still finding the reliable NGO's, so that they can perform their duties towards the society. Those companies who are operating and working on rural or semi rural areas they need the help of local NGO's so that they can reach out to the needy people.

Considering the huge sum of funds at stake for the relief efforts, corporate are struggling not just in finding a reliable NGO partner but also in figuring out a way to monitor and track the use of these funds and assessing their impact.

The study has shown that many corporate who are looking for NGO partners working in the areas where they have factories, plants or other setups. Those in remote or rural areas are especially well-versed with the existing challenges of those communities and the compounding effect that COVID-19 would have. Moreover, they feel connected to the struggles of those in the area after having worked there.

Concluding the above all factors it is rightly said that NGO's can act as a bridge between the corporate and the society and can bring out the significant changes in the long run with the unique and innovative approach . The dire need is to make this model as a best fit model and to explore the horizons for the overall growth of entire humanity which in turn lead to sustainability.

1) NGO can act as a bridge between the corporate and the society.

2) An hour bring the new sustainable model.

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